

Environmental and Social Performance towards Innovative Green Furniture Marketing Strategy in Bangkok Metropolis

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 08,2025</p> <p>Accepted: September 10,2025</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Environmental performance, Social performance, Innovative green furniture marketing strategy, Sustainability, Metropolitan Bangkok</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17094973</p>	<p><i>Thailand, as a country with abundant forest resources and one of the major timber export country in South Asia region is worth the attention to further investigate on environmental and social performance in green furniture industry. Thailand's Bangkok capital as central city will be our research target in this study. The purpose of this research is to investigate current market situation of green furniture in terms of environmental and social performance, propose some green strategies which pushed by market factor and stakeholder pressure, and these green marketing strategies have impact on social and environmental performance. Using a confirmatory documentary qualitative analyses research method, this study reviewed some comprehensive literatures and found that green material, green product and Eco-design, green price, green service and green brand image have a significant impact on environmental and social performance. It was suggested that an innovative green strategy can be adopted to developed country, since consumers in these countries usually with high awareness on environmental protection and physical health, and relatively with strong purchasing power. For developing countries, Thailand, some consumers have high awareness on environmental and health and with high purchasing power, while others are price sensitive and willing to sacrifice the green attributes for lower price. Thus, a mix of innovative green and non-green strategies were suggested to implement in the country. Social performance is an important influencing factor when making marketing decisions and it can create a good green brand image to differentiate the product as well.</i></p>

Introduction

The environmental resources of the world are depleting slowly, and organizations can no longer ignore these raising concerns (Dubey, Gunasekaran and Ali, 2015). That makes businesses and consumers today confront one of the biggest challenges – to protect and preserve the earth's resources and the environment. Conducting business without compromising future generations satisfy their needs has gained importance since 1990s. Carrying out business in a sustainable way has become a central issue for societies in recent times as business realize their role in the deterioration of environment. In current period, an extensive number of researches identified that go green is imperative for an organization. The practices aiming toward environmental sustainability are becoming a common practice for developed and responsible organizations (Cronin, Smith, Gleim, Ramirez and Martinez, 2011).

On the other hand, in pace with the improvement of social civilization and the development of information environment, the government and the public are paying more and more attention to corporate social performance nowadays. As we can see, social performance is widely recognized in academicians and practitioners. It has become to be one of the important dimensions today while making the marketing decision (Lahouel, Zaied, Song and Yang, 2021).

Under this background, with the rapid economic development globally, people have more money to improve and decorate their living space, which including invest more on furniture. As several previous academicians have already noticed that more and more consumers today with environment and health consciousness that led to huge demand for green furniture. Many prior researches have suggested, demand for green furniture is increasing worldwide (Shahsavar, Kubeš and Baran, 2020).

Thailand, a primarily Buddhist country, the largest economies and business center in Southeast Asia has historically paid close attention on environmental and social issues. Bangkok is Thailand's capital and a metropolis that dwarfs the country's other cities in terms of both size and economic importance. However, research on environmental and social performance on green furniture in Thailand is just getting started when compare to other developing countries (Nuttavuthisit and Thøgersen, 2017). As one of the main timber export country, it is clearly seen that forest area was dramatically decreased in Thailand according to the survey by the

Royal Forest Department, in this survey, the forest area was decreased from 48.21% in 1973 to 31.58% in 2017 of the country areas and these felled woods was cut to be used for housing construction or make furniture (Royal Forest Department, 2018; Anuntaruttana andRoopsing, 2020). Therefore, understanding the current market state for green furniture in Bangkok metropolis area, implementing a sustainable development growth road which is oriented by environmental and social performance for the furniture industry and guiding customers switching their consumption from traditional furniture to green furniture products gradually is particularly important for Thailand. As a consequence, it is worth our attention to further examine on the issue of environmental and social performance towards green furniture market in Bangkok metropolis area.

Definitions

Green Product and Green Furniture

A green product is the product which have a positive impact on the environment or alternatively decrease the negative impact on the environment and it should no danger to the health of human (Cherian and Jacob, 2012). There is no standard definition of green furniture currently, but previous researcher has reached some consensus on the concept of green furniture. Eneizan, Abd Wahab and Obaid (2016) argue that any furniture which is designed to minimize damage and negative impact to the environment and doesn't cause any harm to human during the product lifecycle's stages may be considered as green furniture.

It was noted that green furniture has some common attributes. For example, often symbolized by natural materials, like bamboo is perfect examples of green furniture which made from nature material as bamboo grows so quickly and spreads so widely. Green furniture was also symbolized by used renewable, recyclable, discarded, or other sustainable materials. Besides what were mentioned above, green furniture should lend itself as low toxic levels, durable enough to last, easy repair, assembly, disassembly, recycling and repurposed. Usually, government will intervene in economic activities through various ways, for example, considering green consumption subsidy and non-green consumption tax, in order to encourage green product consumption then further encourage manufacturers improve their environmental performance and effectively balance the social responsibility with corporate profit (Madani and Rasti-Barzoki, 2017).

Non-Green products and non-green furniture

Green products represent a significant improvement in greenness, which can be either small or large, whereas "non-green" refers to no or an insignificant improvement in greenness. Green furniture provides the products and services with lower environmental impacts and perceived to have a positive (or less negative) influence on the environment, while non- green furniture on the other hand do not engage in pro-environmental products and services (Dangelico and Pontrandolfo, 2010).

Sustainability Performance

Sustainability refers to the company's ability to meet its needs without compromising future generations (Maldonado-Erazo, Álvarez-García, del Río-Rama and Correa-Quezada, 2020). The implementation results of the sustainability performance are the basis for the success of businesses in the 21st century as the short-term profit oriented without properly taken into account the long-term sustainability factor might have integrated too many risk factors into companies' performance. So, nowadays, the focus of every organization around the world is on how they can improve their overall business performance and most of the them are emphasizing on 'sustainability performance' which focuses on the environmental, social, and economic performance in a sustainable way. This sustainable development road tries to find a balance among economy, society, and environment performance as a whole. In the furniture industry, sustainability is mostly subject to materials selection for product design, as well all stages of the value chain such as production and packaging (Nakruang, Donkwa and Suvittawat, 2020).

As prior researcher has suggested, furniture categories are mainly panel and steel-wooden ones. For example, China's furniture export structure includes wood furniture (40%), followed by paper (34%) and plywood (10%) in 2015. When comes to children's furniture, the research findings show that 83% of respondents selected solid wood as their favorite material. A survey by Searce (2002) for European Union (EU) market also show the similar results say that wooden furniture accounted for nearly three-quarters (75%) of EU imports back in 2000 (Wan and Toppinen, 2016; Searce, 2002). So, it can conclude that the main raw material in furniture industry is still wood or wood-based products. That makes this industry becomes practically important to enhance long-term sustainability development road. As traditional firms usually emphasis on profit and there are a lot of prior study on economic performance already, so, this research will mainly study on social performance and environmental performance from aspects of green furniture in metropolis Bangkok area.

Social Performance

Younis, Sundarakani and Vel (2016) indicates that social performance is the subsequent outcome of an organization's development of principles, policies, programs and processes of social responsibility and social responsiveness that contribute towards the well-being of the society and it usually related to firm's societal relationship. Social performance and social responsibility have been used interchangeably in prior studies. However, some differences do exist. While social responsibility refers to the obligation and the accountability toward society, social performance refers to the outcomes and results of social responsibility activities. Thus, social performance can be envisaged as doing good through social responsibility initiatives and doing bad through corporate social irresponsibility untoward events (Price and Sun, 2017). In short, social responsibility is about activities and social performance is about outcomes.

Environmental Performance

In recent decades, environmental problems have become an increasing concern for the general public (i.e. governments, companies, and consumers) as well as academia around the world as many emerging countries face serious environmental deterioration. Whether an enterprise is striving to solve environmental problems and improve the environmental performance have become a critical issue in today's global economy. Environmental performance level is how successfully organization can decrease hazardous substances, other dangerous and toxic materials to lower its effect on natural environment and it is the ability to reduce air emissions, effluent waste and solid waste and decreased the frequency for environmental accidents as well. Some previous researchers argue that businesses around the world are beginning to recognize the appeal of environmentally friendly products and strategies, as well as the growing importance of going green as a feasible organizational approach with real consequences for marketing. Green product is becoming a global trend, and this trend is pulled by the consumers, spurred by government regulations, and implemented by industries (Jakob and Edenhofer, 2014).

Conceptual framework

Figure 1 implies the previous conceptual frameworks of the current study, which is outlines that driver as a dynamic factor behind the decision of implementing green marketing strategies into the organization. Afterward, the manifestation of the organization's green marketing strategies support to engender the sustainability in the form of environmental and social performance. According to the model, organizations are now being forced to adopt new green marketing strategies which was pushed by various drivers and these programs obtain superior competitive advantages by generating sustainable performance.

Figure 1 The accumulations of conceptual frameworks of the study

Literature review

A. Drivers

In recent years, researchers have increasingly started to address the drivers of green product and process innovations. Drivers were viewed from different perspectives, for instance, technology-push as a market-pull perspective or from a perspective that focuses on internal factors (e.g., firm's organizational and technological capabilities) vs. external factors (e.g., green demands, regulations and laws, and pressure from competitors), as discussed by Cai and Zhou (Cai and Zhou, 2014). This study will focus on market factors and stakeholder pressure to analyze drivers of green furniture products.

Market Factors

Customers are of great importance, as operating the supply chain is only justified if the products and services are finally "accepted" by customers. The literature illustrates the fundamental role of market demand to introduce green product and green process innovation. Some previous researchers have already suggested that market demand is a key driver of firms' decisions which generating enhance efficiency, reduce energy and hazardous materials usage in production. According to the study, 89% of respondents were fully aware of furniture's eco-friendliness, most consumers have a positive attitude and have expressed great interest in environmental protection and environmentally friendly products. Some researchers further indicate that

consumers are agree to give extra price for green products, which ultimately contributes to profitability of the firm (Windiana, Mazwan and Mahdalena, 2021; Majerova, 2015). This trend leads companies are seeking market opportunities in the production and promotion of environmentally friendly products and services. One of the reasons for the purchase of green furniture by customers is for their health, which including health status of their family and their future generation.

Stakeholder Pressure

Pressure from stakeholders is reported in literature as an important driver that motivates firms to engage in green innovation, as industrial firms' pollution and hazardous waste have direct and indirect effects on stakeholders. Furniture industry in manufacturing sector is dealing with this distress specifically, because of the rising environmental concerns among its stakeholders. According to the data analysis results from Ara, Yeap & Hassan (2020), stakeholders' pressures positively influence the adoption of green marketing strategies at $\beta = 0.415$, $p < 0.01$.

Existing and anticipated government environmental regulations, taxes and subsidies based on firms' environmental impact are assumed to have an influence on corporate green marketing programs (Zhang, Liu, Ge, Hao and Hao, 2021). The government regulations are reported in many studies as main influencing factor to motivate firms to engage in going green decision as green strategies are direct consequence of government interventions designed to promote environmental responsibility. To deal with the legitimacy pressure from the government, enterprises as individuals will strive to develop green products and adopt green marketing strategies to meet the government's legitimacy standards. Moreover, regulatory measures and incentives may smooth the way for firms to enter into markets for green products.

From a worldwide standpoint, governments are paying more attention to environmental and climate issues than ever before. In the report of the 19th National Congress, The People's Republic of China (China) government proposed to developing China into a "prosperity, strength, democracy, civilization, harmony and beauty" country. The word "beauty" was proposed first time. Moreover, it has declared their carbon-neutral plan of its economy in September 2020. Besides China, other countries are also lining up to set new climate targets for the middle of the century. On October 2020, Japan proclaimed that it would eliminate all greenhouse gases. South Korea have declared that their economies will be carbon-neutral, meaning that they will put no more carbon dioxide into the atmosphere than they take out on September as well. In March the European Union unveiled a "net-zero" plan of its own. Britain and France have enshrined their targets into law. Meanwhile, the victory on greenhouse gases for Joe Biden put America on a similar path (The Economist, 2020). All these measurements suggest that more and more countries are paying much attention on climate and environment issues, increasing concern on environment is a global trend.

Various individual and institutional stakeholders are also influence firm's decision to initiate green marketing strategies, these stakeholders including suppliers, customers, competitors, employees and industrial associations., etc. (Lin, Zeng, Ma, Qi and Tam, 2014). Institutional pressures can prompt green marketing programs, particularly in corporations exhibiting perceived deficiencies in environmental responsibility. Competitor's involvement in green innovation pressurizes organizations to go green, as external pressure is viable mechanism to encourage firms to adopt green innovation. The critical role of suppliers was also investigated in new green product innovation and it could range in the whole lifecycle of product. Moreover, it is possible that suppliers may boycott firm's products that having negative impact on the environment to defend their own image. The literature also reports significance of internal stakeholders i.e., managers, leaders and supervisors in stimulating green marketing programs in firms.

B. Marketing Strategies affecting Social and Environmental Performance on Green furniture products

The global environmental realization has demanded the organizations to modify their motivation from only economic performance to environmental and social performance with higher economic returns. Thus, organizations all over the world are leading their activities to lock social sustainability. Some scholars have broadly stressed the outcome of social performance while conducting green movements into the organizations. Hence, in fact, it is accredited by several authors that green marketing strategies is a great platform to generate profit by ensuring improved social and environmental performance through instigating a fitness between traditional business practices and environmental anxieties. one strategy called "supplier management for risks and performance" request additional environmental and social criteria are taken into supplier evaluation to avoid risk when related problems are raised, environmental and social standards play a central role in enabling this.

It was found that green marketing strategies have substantial effect on social performance, social performance had the highest attainment level when apply green marketing practices (Mitra and Datta, 2014). This finding

reinforces previous theories on the important role of green marketing strategies to social performance. As research notes the numerous benefits offered to firms utilizing socially responsible strategies, it is likely that the number of firms enacting such strategies to increase their performance will continue to rise. To be short, social aspect is one of the important dimensions today while making the marketing decision.

Except the important role of social performance, firms are paying special attention on environmental concerns nowadays also in order to differentiate their products from competitors as well as to enter the emerging markets of green products. Environmental sustainability has been proposed as an alternative strategy to earn money through contributing to solving environmental problems. Better environmental performance may facilitate new market opportunities (Cheng, Yang and Sheu, 2014). Thus, many organizations are amending their benchmark by integrating environmental goals as obligatory regulations or voluntary movements to secure higher environmental performance. Through achieving this environmental performance, an organization can lessen the environmental atrocity of its business operations and can advance its competitive lead.

On the other side, some researchers suggested that environmental performance have positive impact on economic performance in the long run and it can improve companies' competitiveness. Bassetti, Blasi and Sedita (2021) provide an empirical evidence and confirms that environmental performance positively affects returns on assets and equity by considering a panel of 998 US companies which were observed over the period 2003–2017. They claim that green firms tend to be more efficient in generating future wealth although the cost increase in the short term. And a major intervention to reduce environmental impact as part of a proactive environmental strategy can increase a firm's sustainable competitiveness in national and global markets.

The study investigated by Micheli, Cagno, Mustillo and Trianni (2020) stated a positive association between green marketing strategies and environmental performance. More detailed, green purchasing, eco-design and packaging have significant impact on the environmental performance where ($\beta = 0.445$) at level of significance (0.006) and ($\beta = 0.293$) at level of significance (0.002) separately. An evidence of green products, green prices to have a positive effect on firms' environmental performance were also founded. A new idea that environmental performance is in the interest of local governments providing another perspective for understanding corporate social responsibility. Green marketing strategies to protect the environment and contribute to the society play an intervening role among drivers, social performance and environmental performance. Adopting an eco-friendly strategy in a company is part of its social responsibility.

Recommendation

The Marketing Strategies towards Innovative Green Furniture Products

Many marketers and companies now use environmental issues as a way to attract public interest and create a green company image. Green furniture is one of this kind of product which implement green marketing as an environmentally friendly marketing strategy. Green marketing strategies are carried out by the company as the company's responsibility for the environment as well as to meet the needs and desires of consumers for environmentally friendly products. It encompasses all the organizational activities in green related to the modifications in products, pricing, distribution, communication, employee benefits, processes, and atmosphere in an environmental way. Below are some aspects of green marketing strategies that this study believe it may bring benefits to the organization if it was implemented properly.

Green Design

Every business needs to develop an eco-friendly design which have the capability of minimizing pollution and hazards. Green design, also known as eco-design, designs for the environment, environmentally conscious design, life cycle design and sustainable design, is a new industrial design approach guided by saving resources and protecting the environment by emphasizing the development of green products during its whole lifecycle. Previous researchers ever indicated that green design is the core of green furniture products and shows there is significant positive impact of the eco-design on the environmental-based marketing performance (Xiong, Ma, Wu and Zhang, 2020). Thus, Green furniture firms should design the product, production and delivery process in ways that more sustainable to better save natural resource and protect environment since the beginning stage, and this design should consider the whole life cycle of one green furniture, from product development till disposal of that green furniture.

Green Materials

Green material should be kinds of material which are renewable, abundant, coming from a variety of natural resources and having a low environmental effect on their production process. It mainly refers to materials that not only have excellent functional use, but also have coordination coexistence and comfort with the ecological environment throughout the entire life cycle of materials. It is non-polluting, energy efficient, durable, long live,

easy to maintain and repair, low waste, capable of being reused and recycled. Green materials selection is the material basis and prerequisite of green furniture products. The recent research found that green material selection has positive impact on environmental performance (Katsutoshi, Kiyoshi, Yoshikazu and Kohmei, 2007). Timber and timber products, recycled materials and other natural materials were considered as green materials. Because wood has a wonderful touch feeling, it works well in sound absorption, humidity stabilization, and air purification also; these characteristics contribute to making wood as one of the healthiest furniture materials. The environmentally friendly properties of recycled materials (such as metal, corrugated paper, and biodegradable plastics) and other rapidly growing and widely distributed natural materials (such as reeds, straw, rattan, and bamboo) led to their selection as green materials suitable for furniture-making as well (Pearson, 1998).

Green product

All business is having responsibility to reduce the environmental pollution in their production process. Green products or environmental products are designed to protect or improve the environment by saving energy or resources and reducing or eliminating toxic waste, pollution, and the use of toxic substances. The green product is used naturally, made from non-toxic, recycled material, or with less packaging/eco-packaging and it has no side effects or having little damage on natural environment. Compared with traditional products, they may be decomposable, renewable, reusable, and/or recyclable, and have little impact on the environment. Green products not only pose less risk to the environment but also bring high living standards to consumers and society. In the case of realizing the importance of the environment, many consumers also realize that their purchasing behavior will have an impact on the ecological environment. Consumers began to change their lifestyles and business activities, and gradually tended to increase consumption of green products (Kong, Harun, Sulong and Lily, 2014). Green products are regularly considered healthier and safer than other regular products and they reduce the utilization of natural assets and the negative impact on the product's life-cycle (Albino, Balice and Dangelico, 2009).

The results of Yue, Sheng, She and Xu (2020)'s study indicate the negative effect of price sensitivity on green consumption. They suggest, compared with non-green products, enterprise should transfer consumers' attention to the price of green products through highlighting unique attributes and values of green products, such as healthy, low-carbon, organic, eco-friendly, etc. Additionally, setting a price comparison effect for consumers between different green products, such as displaying green products of different brands separately instead of comparing with non-green products, is important so that consumers can focus on comparing the differences and receive slight differences in prices between different green brands.

According to research of Souri, Sajjadian, Sheikh and Sana (2018), unavailability of green products reduces the use of these products. In additional, the lack of information, specifically concrete information on the capacity of green products to solve and avoid environmental problems causes most customers to become unaware of the significance of green products. Businesses can fill this by using various green promotional strategies. A proper advertising approach to promote peoples' knowledge about green products is another positive factor which push customers to buy green products. After that, attractive packaging can encourage people to buy more green products.

- **Certifications**

The green attribute is a trust attribute that consumers can't recognize it directly, but it can be indirectly recognized through the trustworthy green mark of third party. For example, Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) Certified wooden for green furniture made, this kind of forest certification helps designate wood as a renewable resource and improves the green image of the wood products sector (Poku-Marboah, Juslin, Hansen and Forsyth, 2003). Certification of products and specific initiatives of process certification, can constitute characteristics of environmentally friendly companies. Eco-Labels is another marketing tools for communication of environmental friendliness of products and services.

- **Recycling**

Globally, energy saving, recycling and low carbon are becoming new development modes, and the green industrial revolution has already begun. Promoting green furniture and ecological furniture in an all-round fashion has become a focus of public attention, and probably the only way to achieve the transformation and upgrading of the furniture industry. The importance of adopting circular economy practices is not only to improve the well-being of society but also to achieve sustainable competitive advantages. However, the measures of furniture recycling in all over the world are inadequate. For example, China was reported to produce 6,000 million tons or about 85 million cubic meters (m³)'s municipal waste annually. Furniture recycling has always been a difficult problem in the furniture marketing process. The public recovery of discarded wood furniture has usually several processing pathways: refurbishing on sales in the flea market

influencing the price mechanism of furniture, burning as fuel or as a landfill bringing pressure and pollution to the environment (Zhu and Wu, 2013).

Green Service

Service is not only the front line of direct contact between consumers and product brands, but also the hotbed of cultivating brand reputation and loyalty. In the new media environment, customers tend to communicate, consumers are the center, consumers are service-oriented (Chao, 2020). Service satisfaction communication strategy is an opportunity to build the brand image of green products. Service satisfaction includes pre-sale, on-sale and after-sales service. In the fierce market competition environment, many furniture companies promote the market with large-scale and extensive publicity mode, but the market response is not satisfactory. Under the new media environment, the use of accurate network database for logistics, installation, maintenance and repair services becomes more and more important in furniture industry. In particular, green furniture brands are not products that can be sold all the time because of green alone. Thus, marketers should understand which service is important under what circumstances. Practically pay much attention on delivery, assembly and disassembly service of green furniture.

Based on Wei, Ang and Jancenelle (2018)'s findings, they argue that given green products are qualitatively different from ordinary products, it is important to supply empirical evidence for the effect of customer participation as it relates to consumers' Willingness to pay more. Thus, sustainability-oriented firms should create more engagement opportunities by designing the production, delivery and service process in ways that more customer participation and involvement is allowed. For example, let customer participate partly in furniture design, assembly and make a unique furniture by themselves., etc. Consumers who are inherently skeptical about green products or ill-equipped to choose green products may be positively incentivized by a high level of customer participation.

Green Price

When comes to price of green products. There are two main views among scholars. One is that the consumer is willing to pay more for green products, as it is indeed a fact that going green is expensive in respect of new technology installation and equipment, personnel training, and there are external costs to converse waste into products recycling. The cost added in the final product and makes it with higher price. Some prior researchers states that consumers with high eco-literacy tend to pay more for green products. However, analysts have come up with inconsistent findings on how much more consumers are willing to pay. The Papadopoulos, Karagouni, Trigkas and Platogianni (2010) study indicates that willingness to pay a price premium for green products has been growing for US consumers with an increase of 3% in 2017 comparing to 2010 and consumers are motivated to spend an extra 2%-16% for green furniture. According to a survey in the Federative Republic of Brazil, respondents were willing to pay 10% premium on average for green furniture. Another survey conducted in Europe and the United States with 1,000 responds demonstrated that over 70% of consumers are willing to pay an additional 5% for a green product like furniture if it met the same standards as an alternative one. However, it depends on the price premium, less than 10% of consumers responded that they would choose "green" products if the price premium increased up to 25% (Papadopoulos, Karagouni, Trigkas and Platogianni, 2010; de Medeiros, Ribeiro and Cortimiglia, 2016; Kucher, Heldak, Kucher and Raszka, 2019).

On the other hand, another group of research scholars suggest that customer is price sensitive and not willing to pay more for green products, especially for those consumers with low environmental concern are unlikely to pay more for it. They believe that purchase probability for green product decreases as the price premium increases. Moreover, there is an expectation on the part of consumers that all products offered should be environmentally safe without a need to trade off quality or pay premium prices for them. Therefore, high-cost of green products reduce the use of these products (D'Souza, Taghian and Khosla, 2007; Gan, Wee, Ozanne and Kao, 2008). Therefore, marketers can set up a premium price for green furniture compare to ordinal one, but it should be in a reasonable range, the previous researchers support that it should in the range of 2% - 25%. Furthermore, green products add value and are competitive only if they satisfy core parameters such as quality, functionality and an evident embracement of environmental sustainability.

Green Brand Image

The approximate coefficients suggest that unknown brand have a negative effect on the consumer's probability of purchasing green products. So, to strengthen consumers' awareness of the green impression of the green furniture brand is very important and the concept of green image was highlighted as a primary influence in purchasing decision of green product. The way to create the green brand image has become the top priority of furniture companies today. It helps organizations to gain a competitive advantage and enable them to differentiate their products. In addition, the concept of green management, green marketing and green logo

encapsulates the consumer's awareness and image of green furniture brand, so, it is necessary to strengthen it. Advertising strategy is indispensable for building green brand image as well. Firms should use products, services, advertising, publicity, marketing and other ways to create a good brand image of green furniture. The common means of conveying to the customers include sales promotions, direct marketing, public relations and advertising which convey the core message of greenness to the customer. When developing an advertising strategy to strength the green brand image, in this digital media environment era, it is necessary to use not only the traditional media, but also various new media, such as websites, e-magazines, blog ads, and other digital social media. What's more, the recovery of packaging and products can improve corporate image (Rennings, 2000).

Conclusion

Basically, the purpose of this study is to analyze whether the various of drivers can influence the decision of adopting green marketing strategies and what is the actual worth of implementing green marketing strategies in attaining social and environmental performance.

From the literature review, out of 150 research papers, around 120 papers are taking about green products (account for 80%) or relevant issues, it is clearly observed to conclude that green products, environmental performance and social performance were generated widespread concerns. In today's fierce competition business world, green product is trend of today's market comparing with conventional non-green products. Market factors, or huge demand on green products becomes a very important driver to impact on company's decision making to adopt green marketing strategies. As in furniture industry, the factor of green innovation is usually related to material selection, so, the green material is the most important factors which will influence on environmental and social performance.

A specific conclusion that can be drawn from this study findings is that companies have the potential to adopt green marketing strategies as their strategic movement to accomplish their sustainability goals. Many furniture firms have realized the importance to adopt green marketing strategies, it can achieve by use green material, eco-design the furniture during furniture's whole life cycle, set appropriate price for green furniture, provide good service on pre-sale, on-sale and after sale stages, all these measurements can help companies create good brand image. Green material, green product & eco-design, green service and green brand image have significant impact on social performance and environmental performance. When comes to price of green furniture, some researcher say that customer is willing to pay average 10% more for green furniture, while another group of researchers claim that customer is very price sensitive and not willing to pay more for green furniture.

At point of this time, the demand for different countries is different. For developed countries, customer with strong purchase power and pay much attention on their environmental and health, it is more suitable to introduce green products for them and adopt green marketing strategy. However, from another aspect, there are still many developing countries in the world which not care much about green products and customer (especially elderly customer). There has low awareness on environmental and health issues. These countries and large-scale segment market, furniture companies can still promote conventional non-green furniture.

Thailand is one of the relatively developing countries in Southeast Asia, with Bangkok standing as the country's economic center. Bangkokian customers have higher purchasing power and with modern consumption concepts than customers in other parts of the country. At the same time, because of the wealth disparity, furniture companies should consider segmenting the consumer market when establishing marketing strategies in order to better meet the needs of each customer group. Firms can promote green furniture products to those consumers with high-income, environmentally conscious and health-sensitive. While it can also consider to promote conventional furniture products to consumers with low and medium incomes and low environmental awareness. In case of non-green furniture, according to several prior researcher's finding, some organizations and consumers have realized the harm of non-green furniture, which may emit harmful gas (such as formaldehyde) to hurt customer's health. A survey from Hong Kong Trade Development Council (HKTDC) in China show that over 90% of respondents are willing to buy green furniture and more than 77% of parents are worried that non-eco-friendly furniture will affect their children's physical health (Xu, Wang and Yu, 2020). According to a large multi-country survey by McKinsey, 87% of consumers surveyed are concerned about the environmental and social impact of the furniture products they buy, 33% say they are willing to pay a premium for green products, 54% care about the environment and want to help tackle climate change (Bonini and Oppenheim, 2008). In the long run, however, with the Thailand economy's continued expansion and consumer awareness increase of environmental preservation and health, it is an inevitable tendency for furniture companies to gradually transition from traditional furniture to green furniture. For Thailand's furniture companies adopt green innovation, green marketing strategies mentioned in this paper on, green material, green product and eco-design,

green price, green service and green brand image is some effective ways to improve social and environmental performance, and further improve higher customer loyalty to bring benefit to the enterprises and enterprisers.

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